

Building AI Capacity Between Beijing and Washington: The Gulf's China Strategy

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What defines cooperation between China and the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) states in high-value technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI)? What drives it, and what are its likely consequences? Set against intensifying US–China rivalry—between the world’s two largest economies and leading AI powers—how are Gulf states, long-standing US security partners, managing the pressure?

The evidence points to strategic hedging. Gulf governments are not aligning exclusively with either Washington or Beijing when it comes to AI. Instead, they are seeking to maximize economic and technological opportunity while limiting political and security exposure. This reflects the national interests and motivations of these governments regarding AI, along with the extent to which they have advanced in developing a deeper and more expansive AI capacity. Moreover, these efforts do not operate in a vacuum, but must also take into account the two models of corporate autonomy and state strategy offered by the US and China. In the US case, it is a market-led approach in which big tech companies have scaled up innovations from venture capital-funded AI labs. Meanwhile, the Chinese model is one where the state has a greater role in directing and coordinating

national corporations in technology transfer and AI.

The United States remains the dominant external security actor in the Gulf and the wider Middle East. GCC states appear committed to maintaining this status quo. Qatar hosts US Central Command, the US Fifth Fleet operates from Bahrain, and Washington has designated several Gulf partners—including Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, and Qatar—as major non-NATO allies (Sentner 2025). Gulf states remain among the largest purchasers of US defense systems. High-level diplomacy reinforces this architecture: President Trump’s regional visit in May 2025 and Crown Prince Mohammed bin Salman’s White House meeting in November 2025 underscored deep political and economic ties, including Saudi pledges to invest up to \$1 trillion in the US economy (Ratney 2026).

Yet, a security partnership with the US has not translated into economic exclusivity. Gulf governments have diversified partnerships across Europe and Asia, including with Chinese firms (Mogielnicki 2022). Crucially, this engagement has not—at least so far—produced structural technological subordination. Gulf regimes have avoided becoming locked

into Chinese state or corporate control in the AI sector and have signaled ambitions to shape, rather than simply accept, the terms of cooperation.

Elite incentives help explain their visions and actions. Gulf rentier systems historically rested on hydrocarbon revenues that sustained regime durability through patronage, welfare provision, and guaranteed public employment (Beblawi and Luciani 1987). Such arrangements typically dampen reform. However, structural pressures—energy transition, price volatility, demographic and generational shifts, and technological disruption—have altered elite calculations. Economic models anchored solely in hydrocarbons are increasingly exposed.

This recognition has driven diversification programs over the past decade, including Saudi Vision 2030, UAE Vision 2031, and Qatar National Vision 2030. While differing in emphasis, all aim to reduce reliance on oil and gas rents and expand into various high-value sectors, including advanced manufacturing, digital infrastructure, and AI (Bazoobandi 2025). Initiatives to encourage AI development range from Saudi Arabia's \$100 billion Project Transcendence to the UAE's G42 partnerships with firms such as TSMC, Samsung, and Microsoft Azure.

Diversification attempts in the Gulf have a long history, dating back to the 1970s in Saudi Arabia and Oman, and later in the rest of the region. Earlier waves faltered for multiple reasons. Investment cycles tracked hydrocarbon revenues: when oil prices rose, diversification expanded; when they fell, those measures stalled. Among the reasons for this happening were tied to the heavy reliance on state support and insufficient independent forms of assistance through the private sector

and foreign investment. Additionally, these diversification efforts were not undertaken alongside a rationalization or improvement in efficiency gains in the public sector. There was also insufficient uptake from domestic capital and a continued reliance on migrant labor. As a result, governments retreated to subsidies and public hiring when social resistance intensified (Hvidt 2013).

The current diversification efforts may be different. Sovereign wealth funds in the Gulf have expanded significantly over the past decade, more than doubling from \$2 trillion in assets in 2015 to \$5.35 trillion by 2025. This constitutes more than 40% of all assets under management by sovereign wealth funds around the world (Touazi 2025). These assets provide capital buffers capable of sustaining long-term investment domestically and abroad. Reform has also proceeded incrementally to manage political risk. In Saudi Arabia, for example, this has included selective “authoritarian liberalization” measures such as expanded entertainment sectors and lifting restrictions on women driving in order to recalibrate the social contract without loosening political control (Bassiouni 2022).

China has become central to the current diversification trajectory as well. Previously marginal, China became a net energy importer in 1993, prompting closer regional ties to secure reliable energy for its rapidly growing economy (Huwaitin 2022, Olimat 2023). While the initial focus was on energy, economic exchange and trade have expanded. Chinese contractors became prominent in infrastructure construction under the Belt and Road Initiative. More recently, cooperation has shifted toward telecommunications, 5G networks, fiber-optic infrastructure, data centers, and AI applications under the complementary Digital Silk Road framework

(Chaziza 2025; Aburaya 2025). Firms such as Huawei, ZTE, Alibaba, and Tencent have become embedded in Gulf digital ecosystems, offering competitively priced, integrated technological packages (Mogielnicki 2022).

Washington responded to these developments with varying degrees of caution. As the US-China rivalry intensified around the world, it impacted the AI sector as well, from semiconductor supply chains and critical minerals to data governance, as well as concerns about indirect technology leakage (Huq 2024). During the first Trump and Biden administrations, the US pressed Gulf partners to be wary of economic engagement with Chinese entities (Carcidi and Soliman 2024). Gulf governments, reliant on US security guarantees, sought to manage these sensitivities. The UAE's G42 reportedly divested from certain Chinese partnerships amid American scrutiny (Clemmensen, Redlich, and Rumley 2024). Since Trump's return to the White House, he has taken a less confrontational approach, authorizing advanced semiconductor exports to Saudi Arabia and the UAE despite earlier concerns over potential downstream exposure to Chinese actors (Soliman 2026). In May 2025, he was won over during his visit to the Gulf, where GCC leaders understood his preference for personal and transactional relations which seek to maximize commercial opportunities. Saudi Arabia pledged to invest up to \$600 billion in the US economy – a figure that Mohammed Bin Salman increased to \$1 trillion when visiting the White House later in the year (Unit for Political Studies 2025). In this regard, Trump's foreign policy during the first year of his second term was in line with that of his first term as whole: focused on countering perceived grievances against the rest of the world by advancing "America First" populist nationalism while challenging the precepts of the liberal

international order that the US had both constructed and maintained (Schortgen 2024, Reiss 2026). In the Middle East, this was echoed in ongoing uncertainty and unpredictability, including his attack on Iran with Israel in June 2025 and again in February 2026.

Chinese AI engagement in the Gulf is uneven and reflects the readiness gap between states rather than any preference to align with the Chinese or US approaches to AI – although, as will be observed later, much of the Gulf's current AI infrastructure has been built on the US model and by US providers, which presents challenges in operating independently.

Broadly, Kuwait, Bahrain, and Oman lag in digital infrastructure and AI adoption. By contrast, Saudi Arabia and the UAE have invested heavily in digital transformation and e-government, positioning themselves as regional leaders (Bi et al. 2025). When it comes to AI, Soliman (2025) notes that the UAE was the region's first mover, building regulatory frameworks, data center density, and AI partnerships. Saudi Arabia's advantage is its size and capacity to scale, which it is now doing by building up its institutions and computing power capacity. For the other GCC countries, like Qatar, Oman, Kuwait, and Bahrain, there are varying levels of ambition and interest in terms of what they wish to focus on when it comes to digital technologies and AI. Among them, it is Qatar, along with Saudi Arabia and the UAE, that have attracted the bulk of Chinese AI activity (Ayaz 2025).

Dubai was an early adopter of Chinese technology, embedding facial recognition and behavioral analytics systems in initiatives such as "Police without a Policeman" and "Oyoon" – "Eyes" in Arabic – alongside broader smart-

city and cybersecurity programs (Hasib and Shire 2022). Saudi Arabia has deployed AI tools for Hajj crowd management and proposed to incorporate Chinese-linked technologies into megaprojects such as NEOM, the planned 170-kilometer-long futuristic linear city that was to run from the sea into the desert. However, following delays and the technical and financial challenges of building such a city entirely from scratch in the middle of the desert, coupled with demands on government spending elsewhere, the more fanciful elements around NEOM have been downgraded. In its place, NEOM has been repurposed as a potential hub for large-scale computing infrastructure. The reasons for this shift revolve around its geographical location, from Saudi Arabia's potential to provide connectivity between Europe, Africa, and Asia, as well as its access to the sea and desert: the former providing water to support the cooling systems needed, and the latter, where solar and wind power can be accessed to provide the energy needed for large-scale computing (Chaudhary 2026). As for Qatar, its AI approach with China has been more research-focused, emphasizing smart-city development in Lusail and academic and cloud infrastructure partnerships (Ayaz 2025).

Risks remain in China-GCC AI cooperation. The deployment of surveillance-oriented AI within authoritarian governance frameworks raises human rights concerns. While these concerns may not apply to Trump himself, they certainly do to a large segment of the US political establishment, as well as the private technology sector. Some of these concerns were captured in the narratives presented by the National Security Commission on Artificial Intelligence, which operated between 2019 and 2021 (Retzmann 2024: 238, 241).

Technological transfer is also structurally

limited: Chinese firms typically export mature systems while retaining frontier innovation capacity, leaving the Gulf with capital and markets but little integration into China's core AI developments (Marks 2026a). This reflects Beijing's more state-oriented approach and concern with technological autonomy and risk management – an area that arguably appears less of a cause for concern following Trump's decision to scrap his predecessor's semiconductor export control regime. It may be characterized as a continuation of the "energy-for-industry" dynamic that has shaped China-GCC relations since 1993. In other words, the Gulf countries export hydrocarbons and China exports manufactured and industrial goods. However, such assumptions underestimate Gulf agency, as regional leaders are not content to accept a purely subordinate role (Cheng 2025).

GCC states seek to maximize economic opportunities by accommodating both Chinese and American interests. At the same time, they also pursue independent technological ambitions and are unwilling to be passive recipients of advanced technology. In particular, these states aspire to turn the Gulf into an AI hub with its own related infrastructure. Their objective is not only to serve their own residents, but also to act as a gateway to the wider Global South, including the rest of the Middle East, Africa, and Asia. In doing so, the Saudis and Emiratis envisage themselves as offering an alternative third option to the infrastructure provided and powered by American and Chinese entities (Marks 2026a, 2026b). Additionally, the Gulf states aim to use the comparative advantages they have to reach these goals. For instance, the UAE aims to become a regional hub for AI development and integration. Meanwhile, Saudi Arabia intends to invest in rare-earth extraction and processing. It also endeavors to exploit its

cheap energy to support high-performance computing, positioning itself as potentially the third-largest AI market globally (Alrajjal 2025; Ghosh 2025).

That said, Saudi and Emirati ambitions are not without their challenges and risks – all of which may only become apparent with time. For one, the Gulf AI “Third Option” may presume a degree of neutrality between the American and Chinese technological and AI superpowers. However, the reality remains that the bulk of the AI infrastructure of the GCC has been built on US models, chips, and cloud architecture – which means that it can never fully break with Washington and its concerns, including governance. Additionally, other countries in the Global South may be less interested in using the Gulf as an alternative and instead rely on either or both of the superpowers. Regardless of whether the American option is available, these countries turn to the Chinese one because it is cheaper and offers fewer restrictions on governance or regulation. Finally, the approach to AI development and innovation inside and outside the Gulf could change from the current big tech/scaled-up model reliant on large, centralized data centers to smaller and more regionalized hubs (Marks 2026b).

In sum, the Gulf presents a dynamic space within which wider US-China competition is playing out, especially in the AI sector. Gulf states—particularly Saudi Arabia, the UAE, and Qatar—are making use of the opportunities presented by the differences between Washington and Beijing to widen their economic and technological options. Whether it is the market-led AI model associated with the US or the more state-oriented and coordinated version offered by China, both have contributed to the forms and availability of technologies exported to the region. How-

ever, it is important to note that even as GCC states seek to become an alternative AI hub, they will not be able to do so without the input from the two technological superpowers. The efforts of these states to hedge to minimize risk and maximize opportunities remain contingent on the wider geopolitical climate. Should the US veer in a different direction and intensify pressure on GCC countries to disengage from China, coupled with Beijing resisting deeper integration, they could have less space to maneuver.♦

References

- Aburaya, Farah. 2025. “The Future Role of China in the GCC’s Tech Transition,” *Al Habtoor Research Centre*, October 20. <https://www.habtoorresearch.com/programmes/the-future-role-china-gcc/>
- Alrajjal, Tala. 2025. “Saudi Arabia Is Making a Massive Bet on AI,” *CNN*, November 2. <https://edition.cnn.com/2025/11/02/tech/saudi-arabia-ai-powerhouse>
- Ayaz, Behrouz. 2025. “China’s AI Push in the Persian Gulf Region,” *The Diplomat*, 22 Revised. November. <https://thediplomat.com/2025/11/chinas-ai-push-in-the-gulf-region/>
- Bassiouni, Moustapha Chérif. 2022. “Saudi Reforms: Change for Survival or for Progress?” *European Institute of the Mediterranean*. <https://www.iemed.org/publication/saudi-reforms-change-for-survival-or-for-progress/>
- Bazoobandi, Sara. 2025. *The GCC Countries’ Quest for Economic and Digital Transformation*. Hamburg: GIGA.

- Beblawi, Hazem, and Giacomo Luciani. 1987. *The Rentier States in the Arab World*. London: Croom Helm.
- Bi, Ran, Fozan Fareed, Jeong Dae Lee, Sidra Rehman, Yuan Gao Rollinson and Tongfang Yuan. 2025. *Digital Transformation in the Gulf Cooperation Council Economies*. Departmental Paper (April). Washington DC: International Monetary Fund.
- Carcidi, Vincent, and Mohammed Soliman. 2024. *The Role of the Middle East in the US-China Race to AI Supremacy*. Washington DC: Middle East Institute.
- Chaudhary, Isha. 2026. "Saudi Arabia Scales Back the Line Project to Build AI Data Centers," *Parametric Architecture*, March 9. <https://parametric-architecture.com/saudi-arabia-scales-back-the-line/>.
- Chaziza, Mordechai. 2025. "The Great Power Tech Race in the Persian Gulf: A Western Perspective." In *Technology Rivalry Between the USA and China*, ed. Peter Chow. 355-390. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cheng Wang. 2025. "Reflections on the Future Investment Forum," *China-MENA Newsletter*, November 19. <https://chinamenanewsletter.substack.com/p/cheng-wangs-reflections-on-the-recent>
- Clemmensen, Andrew, Rebecca Redlich and Grant Rumley. 2024. "G42 and the China-UAE-U.S. Triangle" *Washington Institute for Near East Policy*, April 3. <https://www.washingtoninstitute.org/policy-analysis/g42-and-china-uae-us-triangle>
- Ghosh, Indranil. 2025. "U.S. gains in AI race as Gulf nations ditch China for chips," *Rest of World*, November 21. <https://restofworld.org/2025/mideast-us-chip-deal-and-china/>
- Hasib, Bassant, and James Shire. 2022. "Cybersecurity in the GCC," *Middle East Policy* 29(1): 90-103.
- Huq, Aziz. 2024 "A world divided over artificial intelligence," *Foreign Affairs*, March 11. <https://www.foreignaffairs.com/united-states/world-divided-over-artificial-intelligence>
- Huwaidin, Mohamed. 2022. "China and the Gulf region: From strangers to partners." In *Routledge Handbook on China-Middle East Relations*, ed. Jonathan Fulton. 81-92. London: Routledge.
- Marks, Jesse. 2026a. "China's AI Cooperation in the GCC," *Coffee in the Desert*, January 6. <https://jessemarks.substack.com/p/chinas-ai-cooperation-in-the-gcc>
- Marks, Jesse. 2026b. "Can the GCC build the third AI option?" *Coffee in the Desert*, February 23. <https://jessemarks.substack.com/p/can-the-gcc-build-the-third-ai-option>.
- Mogielnicki, Robert. 2022. "Technological Dimensions of China-MENA Economic Relations." In *Routledge Handbook on China-Middle East Relations*, ed. Jonathan Fulton. 281-296. London: Routledge.
- Olimat, Muhammad. 2023. "China and the Middle East: An Overview." In *Routledge Companion to China and the Middle East and North Africa*, ed. Yahia Zoubir. 9-24. London: Routledge.
- Ratney, Michael. 2026. "Saudi Arabia's Mohammed bin Salman Got a Lot from Trump. What Did the United States Get?" *Center for Strategic & International Studies*, January 5. <https://www.csis.org/analysis/saudi-arabias-mohammed-bin-salman-got-lot-trump-what-did-united-states-get>

Reiss, Mitchell. 2026. "Trump's Foreign Policy After Year One: A Look Back, A Look Ahead," *Royal United Services Institute*, January 20. <https://www.rusi.org/explore-our-research/publications/commentary/trumps-foreign-policy-after-year-one-look-back-look-ahead>

Retzmann, Nike. 2024. "Winning the technology competition': Narratives, power comparisons and the US-China AI race." In *Comparisons in global security politics* eds. Thomas Müller, Matias Albert and Kerrin Langer. 237-256. Bristol: Bristol University

Press. Schortgen, Francis. 2024. "U.S. Foreign Policy in the Trump Administration: The Unmooring of America's Global Roles?" In *The Legacy of the Trump Administration: A Disruptive Presidency*. ed. Michael Grossman, Francis Schortgen, Ronald Matthews Jr and David Cohen. 121-145. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.

Sentner, Irie. 2025. "Trump elevates Saudi Arabia to 'major non-NATO ally' status," *Politico*, 18 November. <https://www.politico.com/news/2025/11/18/trump-saudi-arabia-ally-00658467>

Soliman, Mohammed. 2025. "From Crude to Compute: Building the GCC AI Stack," *Middle East Institute*, December 10. <https://mei.edu/report/from-crude-to-compute-building-the-gcc-ai-stack/#pt1>.

Soliman, Mohammed. 2026. "US Authorizes Chips for the UAE, Saudi Arabia," *Middle East Institute*, January 28. <https://mei.edu/policymemo/us-authorizes-chips-for-the-uae-saudi-arabia-2/>

Touazi, François-Aïssa. 2025. "Les fonds souverains du Golfe, acteurs majeurs de la finance mondiale" [Gulf sovereign wealth funds, major players in world finance], *Politique étrangère* 90(4): 25-38.

Unit for Political Studies. 2025. "Deals Without Guarantees: Trump's Gulf Visit and the Future of US-Gulf Relations," *Arab Center Washington DC*, May 22. <https://arabcenterdc.org/resource/deals-without-guarantees-trumps-gulf-visit-and-the-future-of-us-saudi-relations/>